

Deliverable D8.4

Dissemination and Communication Report

WP 8

Project Acronym & Number:	smashHit – GA 871477
Project Title:	Smart Dispatcher for Secure and Controlled sharing of Distributed Personal and Industrial Data
Funding Scheme:	Innovation Action
Start date of the project:	01.01.2020
Duration:	36 months
Status:	Final
Dissemination Level:	Public
Authors:	UIBK
Contributors:	All partners
Document Identifier:	smashHit_D8.4_v100.docx
Date:	06.01.2023
Revision:	100
Project website address:	www.smashhit.eu/

Every effort has been made to ensure that all statements and information contained herein are accurate, however the smashHit Project Partners accept no liability for any error or omission in the same.

© 2022 Copyright in this document remains vested in the smashHit Project Partners.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 871477

Project Summary

The objective of smashHit is to assure trusted and secure sharing of data streams from both personal and industrial platforms, needed to build sectorial and cross-sectorial services, by establishing a Framework for processing of data owner consent and legal rules and effective contracting, as well as joint security and privacy preserving mechanisms. The vision of smashHit is to overcome obstacles in the rapidly growing Data Economy which is characterized by heterogeneous technical designs and proprietary implementations, locking business opportunities due to the inconsistent consent and legal rules among different data-sharing platforms actors and operators. The Framework will provide methods and tools, such as Smart Data Dispatcher, to assure common consent over data shared using semantic models of consent and legal rules. The new tools include traceability of use of data, data fingerprinting and automatic contracting among the data owners, data providers, service providers and users. These tools are specifically critical for enormous volumes on data streaming from the usage of mass products with cyber physical features (e.g. vehicles). These data streams offer new opportunities to build innovative services, but their combination with other personal and industrial data is subject to complex ownership and consent aspects, as the data streaming from these products belong to persons or organizations who are owners or users of the products. The project will be based on the solutions developed or under development in previous and current projects (AutoMat, Cross-CPP, CAMPANEO, DALICC etc.). smashHit is driven by two industrial Business Cases involving several existing industrial and personal data platforms owned by the leading data providers in three diverse sectors (automotive industry, insurance, smart city), and will provide three demonstrators of various applications of the developed solutions.

Project Consortium

ATB	Institut für angewandte Systemtechnik Bremen GmbH	Germany
UIBK	University of Innsbruck	Austria
LUH	Leibniz Universität Hannover	Germany
TOG	X/Open Company Limited	United Kingdom
VW	Volkswagen AG	Germany
LN	LexisNexis Risk Solutions (Europe)	Ireland
FVH	Forum Virium Helsinki Oy	Finland
INFT	Infotripla Oy	Finland
ATOS	ATOS Spain	Spain
UBO	Rheinische Friedrich-Wilhelms-Universität Bonn	Germany
AM	ARCTIC MACHINE OY	Finland

More Information

ATB Institut für angewandte Systemtechnik Bremen GmbH (Coordinator)
 Represented for the purposes of signing the Agreement by: Christian Wolff
 E-Mail: wolff@atb-bremen.de
 Phone: +49 (0)421 / 22092 33

Institut für angewandte Systemtechnik Bremen GmbH, ATB
 HRB 13969 HB
 Wiener Straße 1
 28359 Bremen
 Germany
 Web: www.atb-bremen.de/

Dissemination Level

PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Change History

Version	Notes	Date
001	Creation of the document, incorporation of D8.4 contents	01.09.2022
002	Updating the document with dissemination and communication activities.	30.11.2022
003	Updating the document based on inputs from consortium partners.	04.12.2022
004	Merge all the changes into single document.	15.12.2022
100	Finalizing of the deliverable	30.12.2022

Document Summary

This deliverable reports on the outcomes of 36 months of the project for dissemination, communication and community building (period: January 2020-December 2022). It is an updated version of M18 report with final assessment of KPIs. It shows the methodology followed, the instruments and mechanisms used to raise the project awareness, the collaboration policy with other projects and related stakeholders and interested groups. It reports on the KPIs for assessing the progress and impact in the due formal reports. List of events, conferences, interest groups, open source communities, online press, journals, social networks, etc. where the project have taken part at, is included.

Abbreviations

App	Software Application
BDVA	Big Data Value Association
BC	Business Case
CPP	Cyber Physical Products
D	Deliverable
DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan
DoW	Description of Work
EC	European Commission
e.g.	Exempli gratia = for example
EU	European Union
FP7	Framework Programme 7
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
i.e.	id est = that is to say
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Month
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
PR	Public Relations
RTD	Research and Technological Development
SME	Small and Medium Sized Enterprise
T	Task
WP	Work Package

Table of Contents

1	Introduction	7
1.1	Purpose.....	7
1.2	Relation to other Projects	8
1.3	Structure	9
2	The Dissemination and Communication Strategy	10
2.1	smashHit Strategy	10
2.2	Overall Set Up	11
2.3	Main Audience and Stakeholders for Dissemination and Communication.....	12
2.4	Communication and Dissemination Channels and Activities	15
3	The Dissemination Activities and their Sustainability	17
3.1	Project Repository	17
3.2	Social Media and Professional Networks	17
3.3	smashHit Logo.....	18
3.4	smashHit Website.....	18
3.5	Social Media Channels of smashHit.....	19
3.6	Traditional Media and Newspapers	21
3.7	Blog Posts.....	23
3.8	Dissemination in EU technology platforms, co-operations with EU projects.....	24
3.9	Events, Conferences and Journals.....	25
3.10	Final Exhibition	27
3.11	Communication Material.....	28
3.12	Demonstrators' Videos	29
4	Dissemination and Communication Reporting	32
4.1	Success Metrics.....	32
4.2	Changes in the Plan and its Execution due to COVID-19.....	43
5	Conclusions	44
6	References.....	45

List of Figures

Figure 1: Building Blocks for Dissemination and Communication	10
Figure 2: Stakeholder Mapping	11
Figure 3: Dissemination and Communication Channels (1)	15
Figure 4: Dissemination and Communication Channels (2)	15
Figure 5: smashHit Logo	18
Figure 6: smashHit Website	19
Figure 7: smashHit LinkedIn Page	20
Figure 8: smashHit Twitter Page	21
Figure 9: smashHit Spotify Page	22
Figure 10: EBDVF session “An Innovative Approach to Compliant Consent”	28
Figure 11: smashHit Poster	30
Figure 12: smashHit flyer (version for the final event at EBDVF 2022)	31
Figure 13: smashHit Website Audience Overview (Status: December 6, 2022)	34
Figure 14: smashHit Website Audience Behaviour Overview (Status: December 6, 2022)	35
Figure 15: smashHit Website Traffic Acquisition Overview (Status: December 6, 2022)	36
Figure 16: Twitter analytics on the last 28 day period, showing top tweets	37
Figure 17: smashHit – LinkedIn Impressions for December 2021-December 2022 (status: December 7, 2022)	38
Figure 18: smashHit – Identification of the individuals who accessed the smashHit LinkedIn contents based on their job functions.	39
Figure 19: smashHit – Identification of individuals who accessed smashHit LinkedIn content based on the size of their respective companies	39
Figure 20: smashHit – Identification of individuals who accessed smashHit LinkedIn content based on their seniority level	40

List of Tables

Table 1: Definitions of Communication and Dissemination	7
Table 2: Related Projects	8
Table 3: Activities	16
Table 4: Social Media Platforms	18
Table 5: Professional Networks	18
Table 6: smashHit Blog Post Planning and Execution	23
Table 7: Demonstrator Videos BC1 (D6.5)	29
Table 8: Demonstrator Videos BC2 (D7.5)	29
Table 9: Overall Dissemination and Communication smashHit KPIs	32
Table 10: Website Metrics	33
Table 11: Social Media Metrics	36
Table 12: Media Communication and Newsletters Metrics	40
Table 13: Conference and Events Metrics	41
Table 14: Publications Metrics	41

1 Introduction

Deliverable D8.4 provides the dissemination and communication report for the 36 months of the smashHit Horizon 2020 EU project. smashHit recognises that awareness needs to be raised and achieves this by providing meaningful information in informative and engaging ways. Collaboration and communication are vital for achieving a good dissemination outcome. An appropriate dissemination strategy has been presented in detail in D8.1 “Dissemination and Communication Plan” (M3) [1], and this deliverable is basing on it, and is, de-facto its updated version, and is describing the implementation of this plan up to now.

In order to clearly understand the difference between Dissemination and Communication, which will be discussed later in this deliverable, the following comparison between the two is provided in Table 1.

Table 1: Definitions of Communication and Dissemination

	Definition	Objective	Focus	Target
Communication	“brings attention of multiple audiences about your research (in a way that can be understood by non-specialists) and addresses the public policy perspective of EU research and innovation funding” ¹	Inform different audiences about the smashHit project and its purpose.	Raise awareness.	Audiences from various backgrounds and stakeholders.
Dissemination	“sharing research results with potential users - peers in the research field, industry, other commercial players and policy makers” ²	To contribute to the process of science. ²	Make results publicly available to others.	Industry, data owners, research groups, scientific community, policy makers, students, innovators.

1.1 Purpose

The detailed objectives of the project dissemination and communication activity, as described in the smashHit project were:

- To widely disseminate and communicate the project concept, developments and findings to identified stakeholders using effective communication means and strategies.
- By using existing communities related to the project interact with them to disseminate project results, get their feedback and integrating our results in them when possible.
- To create and publish scientific contributions valuable for the related research community.
- To collaborate with other European projects or interest groups in the relevant topics.

¹https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/communication_en.htm

²https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/dissemination-of-results_en.htm

- To participate in appropriate European and worldwide events (workshops, seminars, conferences, etc.) targeted at project topics with the ultimate goal to showcase the project results and subsequently to prepare the way for a successful business development of the project outcomes.
- Analyse the standards applicable for the project and which ones could be followed and contributed by the project.

1.2 Relation to other Projects

This project welcomes collaboration with other projects such as CampaNeo, TRUSTS and other in order to develop innovative solutions, which would contribute to solving the ICT-13-2018-2019: Supporting the emergence of data markets and the data economy challenge. Selected projects related to smashHit are stated in Table 2.

Table 2: Related Projects

Project	Description	Website
CampaNeo	An open platform on which private and public institutions can create campaigns, collect and analyse vehicle data in real time.	https://www.digitale-technologien.de/DT/Redaktion/DE/Standardartikel/Smarte-Datenwirtschaft-Projekte/SDW_campaneo.html https://projekte.ffg.at/projekt/3314668
SPECIAL	“SPECIAL allows citizens and organisations to share more data, while guaranteeing compliance with data protection, thus enabling both trust and the creation of valuable new insights from shared data.”	https://www.specialprivacy.eu
DALICC	Software that supports the automated clearance of rights thus supporting the legally secure and time-efficient reutilization of third-party data sources.	https://dalicc.net
enviroCar	An open citizen platform aimed at traffic and environment monitoring.	https://envirocar.org
AutoMat	“To establish a novel and open ecosystem in the form of a cross-border Vehicle Big Data Marketplace that leverages currently unused information gathered from a large amount of vehicles from various brands.”	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/644657
MyData	“To empower individuals by improving their right to self-determination regarding their personal data.”	https://mydata.org
Cross-CPP	Creating access to sensor data from various industrial sectors to enable new dimension of innovative business ideas.	www.cross-cpp.eu

Project	Description	Website
i3-MARKET	Intelligent, Interoperable, Integrative and deployable open source MARKET place with trusted and secure software tools for incentivising the industry data economy.	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/871754
TRUSTS	Trusted Secure Data Sharing Space aims to develop a data-sharing platform for secure, trustworthy, and GDPR-compliant data exchanges.	https://www.trusts-data.eu
DataVaults	Persistent Personal Data Vaults Empowering a Secure and Privacy Preserving Data Storage, Analysis, Sharing and Monetisation Platform.	https://www.datavaults.eu
WorldKG	Creation of a knowledge graph providing semantic geographic information.	https://www.worldkg.org/
EU Hubs 4 Data	Data Innovation Hubs based on existing key players in this area and connecting with data incubators and platforms, SME networks, AI communities, skills and training organisations and open data repositories. The collaboration was lead by ATB and ATOS but involved all RTD partners.	https://euhubs4data.eu

As discussed in the technical deliverables of the smashHit project, smashHit already has been synergetic with the development of other projects. For example, in some cases (e.g. CampaNeo, Cross-CPP) direct technology adoption and further development has already taken place.

1.3 Structure

The deliverable is structured as follows.

- **Section 1** provides an introduction to the deliverable.
- **Section 2** presents the dissemination and communication strategy that is followed and provides a description of the main goals, focus, channels and audience of the smashHit project.
- Further activities, which help the dissemination, are specified in **Section 3**.
- **Section 4** describes in detail the planned success metrics and their achievement.
- Conclusion of the Dissemination and Communication Report can be found in **Section 5**.

2 The Dissemination and Communication Strategy

In this section, we outline the followed smashHit's dissemination and communication strategy, i.e. its set up and performed activities.

2.1 smashHit Strategy

The building blocks and the organisation of the smashHit communication and dissemination strategy are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Building Blocks for Dissemination and Communication

The strategy followed was divided in 3 main phases, which are described as follows:

- **Discovery (M1-M3):** is the kick-off phase where T8.1 and T8.2 in cooperation with T8.3 and T8.4, as well with the rest of the consortium define the overall building blocks under the communication and dissemination strategy phases that the project plans to follow up. It collects the initial insights about channels, target audiences, website, logo, social networks, newsletters, communication material, events and conferences, KPIs, reporting plans, among other key topics, which encompass this task.
- **Launch & Engage (M6-M12-M18):** after the initial set-up, it is expected that the project advances in developing research content and defines clear R&D&I topics where the dissemination actions might start. In addition, the experience and success metrics collected within Business Cases (BCs), Scenarios and Components specification would allow to create relevant content about the results and advances obtained to be communicated through the different channels and target audiences. This would led to the generation of valuable material about smashHit value proposition, benefits, advantages that was incorporated into the messages and communication created to external audiences.
- **Boost Involvement (M18-M36):** given the timeframe of this phase when early prototypes are ready and final prototypes are planned in the following 12 months, smashHit aims to open-up their networks incorporating feedback and continuous interaction exchange from external end-users and stakeholders. This engagement evolved into the appearance of business development joint-actions for the smashHit Framework or for the Business Cases replication and extension. It is also the phase where the project focused on sharing the Lessons Learned and Best Practices in secure and privacy-preserving data-sharing frameworks to the public through whitepapers and scientific publications. All the phases in the Boost Involvement have been completed successfully and more details are in the following sections.

2.2 Overall Set Up

Within this chapter the focus of our dissemination & communication strategy, the communication channels as well as the main target audiences are identified.

GOALS: The main goal of smashHit is to ensure trusted and secure sharing of data streams from both personal and industrial platforms, needed to build sectorial and cross-sectorial services, by establishing a framework for processing of data owner consent, legal rules and effective contracting, as well as joint security and privacy preserving mechanisms.

CORE MESSAGE: The objective of smashHit is to assure trusted and secure sharing of data streams from both personal and industrial platforms, needed to build sectorial and cross-sectorial services, by establishing a Framework for processing of data owner consent and legal rules and effective contracting, as well as joint security and privacy preserving mechanisms. The vision of smashHit is to overcome obstacles in the rapidly growing Data Economy, which is characterized by heterogeneous technical designs and proprietary implementations, locking business opportunities due to the inconsistent consent and legal rules among different data-sharing platforms actors and operators.

The smashHit program has delivered a framework and best practice for traceable data sharing and contracting with consumer consent for scenarios such as advanced smart city solutions or connected car insurance programs. In the same way, smashHit addressed the needs of businesses and consumers for the development of smart mobility solutions in a smart city context with sharing of personal data and traffic information. Unlike other initiatives, smashHit was formed by a consortium of nine organisations drawn from academia, analytics, data security and private enterprise working collaboratively to deliver the benefits of car connectivity to the consumer mass-market.

FOCUS: Scientific publications, communication and dissemination to broader audience and relevant stakeholders, particularly in relation to promoting a more general level innovation action, EU data economy, innovating new services, etc.

We intended spending some time on stakeholder mapping, to identify the critical groups that can contribute the most to the program's success. We have included an example of this below (Figure 2) where the stakeholders are ranked by interest (how interested are they in our program) and power/influence (how much authority or influence they have in our program).

Figure 2: Stakeholder Mapping

These were significant cross-country groups and within the time allocated to the project for communication, we could be at risk of spreading ourselves thinly. The purpose of this exercise was to identify which stakeholders need specific plans, and the priority of communication planning. We investigated that the major groups were the EU, consumers, smart cities, insurers and car OEM's that required individual plans to be created. Journalists, regulators and trade associations were managed as the program develops.

EXPLOITATION: The project's results that will be exploitable after the end of the project can be also disseminated with the channels developed in the project. According to the EU contract, the smashHit website is maintained for after the project's end, as requested. However, exploitation related issues were handled in the scope of Task 8.3 / 8.4 and deliverables D8.2 [2], D8.3 [3], D8.5 [4] & D8.6 [5].

CHANNELS: Our channels include social media, press, web presence, newspapers and articles in journals, conferences and workshops, presentations, organizing or participating in events. Channels to be confirmed on completion of stakeholder mapping exercise (main audience). We anticipated a focus on trade and technical press, consumer press and conference attendance.

2.3 Main Audience and Stakeholders for Dissemination and Communication

As specified in the project proposal, the consortium has already envisioned key groups that were targeted. The dissemination addressed the following stakeholders with according activities:

- **Industry**
With this project we aimed to address industries such as in the sectors of Technology, Insurance, Vehicle Manufacturing (Volkswagen³, Nissan⁴, Ford⁵), Transport, Big Data (Sciencesoft⁶, Hdata Systems⁷, Altoros⁸, Andersen⁹, Thirdeye Data¹⁰), Experienced users and everyday users.
REASON: To further publicise and contribute to our good practice recommendation and acted as mentors.
ACTIVITIES: Newsletters, briefings, website, social media, exhibitions.
- **Policy makers**
Organizations that specialize in privacy, security and policies (IAPP¹¹, White & Case¹², Dentons¹³, Huntonak¹⁴, Bird&Bird¹⁵, EDPB¹⁶).
REASON: To co-create and use our evidence-based policy recommendations.
ACTIVITIES: Workshops, conferences, demonstrations, briefings, newsletters, website, social media, exhibitions.
- **Smart Cities**
Companies that focus on building smart cities that harness the power of technology to increase

³ <https://www.volkswagenag.com>

⁴ <https://www.nissan.at>

⁵ <https://www.ford.com>

⁶ <https://www.scnsoft.com>

⁷ <https://www.hdatasystems.com>

⁸ <https://www.althoros.com>

⁹ <https://andersenlab.com>

¹⁰ <https://thirdeyedata.io>

¹¹ <https://iapp.org>

¹² <https://www.whitecase.com/law/practices/data-privacy-cybersecurity>

¹³ <https://www.dentons.com/en/find-your-dentons-team/practices/privacy-and-security>

¹⁴ <https://www.huntonak.com/en/practices/privacy-and-cybersecurity/>

¹⁵ <https://www.twobirds.com>

¹⁶ https://edpb.europa.eu/edpb_en

operational efficiency (Cisco¹⁷, Schneider Electric¹⁸, Siemens¹⁹, Oracle²⁰, FVH²¹).

REASON: To co-create and use our evidence-based policy recommendations.

ACTIVITIES: Workshops, conferences, demonstrations, briefings, newsletters, website, social media, exhibitions.

- **Students**

Bachelor, Master and PhD student who are interested in innovation, technology, machine learning, mobility/transport, Big Data and security.

REASON: To use our training materials and good practise recommendations and act as mentors.

ACTIVITIES: Online and offline courses, course materials, briefings, scientific publications, conferences, demonstrations, workshops, newsletters, exhibitions.

- **Innovators**

People interested in technology, science, transport who want to be active.

REASON: To use our training materials and good practise recommendations and act as mentors.

ACTIVITIES: Briefings, scientific publications, conferences, demonstrations, workshops, newsletters, exhibitions.

- **Related Projects**

Collaboration with projects that received funding in the same call as smashHit: such as **I3-MARKET**⁷³, TRUSTS, DataVaults²², and a number of others.

REASON: To use our training materials and good practise recommendations and act as mentors.

ACTIVITIES: Briefings, scientific publications, conferences, demonstrations, workshops.

- **smashHit builds on the outcomes of and collaborate with the projects such as** CampaNeo, enviroCar [6], MobGeoSen [7], DALICC²³ [8], Cross-CPP²⁴.

REASON: To contribute and provide further publicity for our outputs.

ACTIVITIES: Briefings, scientific publications, conferences, demonstrations, workshops, newsletters, exhibitions.

- **Scientific Community**

Research groups that focus on Data Analytics (Smart Data Analytics²⁵, Data Science and Evolution²⁶), Semantic Technology (STLab²⁷), Data Visualization (Stanford Visualization Group²⁸), Traceability, Security and Privacy (Center for Information Technology Policy (CITP)²⁹, SecUnity³⁰),

¹⁷ <https://www.cisco.com>

¹⁸ <https://www.se.com/us/en/>

¹⁹ <https://new.siemens.com/global/en.html>

²⁰ <https://www.oracle.com/index.html>

²¹ <https://forumvirium.fi/en/projects/>

²² <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/871755>

²³ <https://www.dalicc.net>

²⁴ www.cross-cpp.eu

²⁵ <http://sda.cs.uni-bonn.de>

²⁶ <https://www.helsinki.fi/en/researchgroups/data-science-and-evolution>

²⁷ <https://www.istc.cnr.it/en/group/stlab?page=2>

²⁸ <http://vis.stanford.edu>

²⁹ <https://citp.princeton.edu>

³⁰ <https://it-security-map.eu>

Machine Learning (AMLab³¹), Artificial Intelligence (The Alan Turing Institute³², IBM Research³³), Database Systems (Dresden Database System Group³⁴). More research groups could be found on the CLAIRE Research Network³⁵. smashHit will also aim at research conference attendees and readers of scientific journals.

REASON: To continue our good practice recommendations, conduct research in the identified gaps and develop student's skills.

ACTIVITIES: Scientific publications, conferences, demonstrations, workshops, newsletters, exhibitions.

- **Start Ups**

smashHit would address Start-Ups in Technology (UiPath³⁶, Improbable³⁷, SIGFOX³⁸), Transport (AUTO1 Group³⁹, Glovo⁴⁰) and Business (Atom Bank⁴¹, Monzo⁴²).

REASON: To further publicise and contribute to our good practice recommendation and act as mentors.

ACTIVITIES: Scientific publications, conferences, demonstrations, workshops, newsletters, exhibitions. **Standardisation Bodies**

Opportunity to collaborate towards extending existing standards and developing new specifications that enable an open ecosystem of components for developing IoT focused applications and services that address user data consent/control requirements, for example in ISO⁴³ and BSI⁴⁴. Possible collaboration with standardization bodies such as OMG⁴⁵ and W3C⁴⁶.

REASON: To further publicise and contribute to our good practice recommendation and act as mentors, to collaborate and help extend existing standards.

ACTIVITIES: Scientific publications, conferences, demonstrations, workshops, newsletters.

In conclusion, we aimed at diverse audiences to make sure that the project could be recognized by as many people as possible. Different groups of people would require a different dissemination approach, which we had envisioned and planned ahead. The dissemination activities were performed by all project partners, but they differ according to what the partners specialize in. Industrial partners approached relevant industry sectors as well as their distributors and client networks, while the academic and research partners worked on disseminating the project to the research community across Europe (and also the world). Feedback from all stakeholders is valuable for the project's activities and thus the feedback from the project partners and other audiences were incorporated throughout smashHit's work.

³¹ <https://mlplatform.nl/researchgroups/machine-learning-group-university-of-amsterdam/>

³² <https://www.turing.ac.uk>

³³ <https://www.research.ibm.com>

³⁴ <https://www.db.inf.tu-dresden.de>

³⁵ <https://claire-ai.org/network/>

³⁶ <http://uiopath.com>

³⁷ <http://improbable.io/>

³⁸ <http://www.sigfox.com>

³⁹ <https://www.auto1-group.com/>

⁴⁰ <https://glovoapp.com/>

⁴¹ <https://www.atombank.co.uk/>

⁴² <https://monzo.com>

⁴³ <https://www.iso.org/home.html>

⁴⁴ <https://shop.bsigroup.com>

⁴⁵ <https://www.omg.org>

⁴⁶ <https://www.w3.org>

2.4 Communication and Dissemination Channels and Activities

The Communication and Dissemination Channels and Activities have been chosen while having in mind different online and off-line scenarios. With them we aimed to address the multiple target audiences identified to perform concrete actions and to widespread specific messages which enhance the awareness and knowledge sharing of the smashHit project concept and its progress during its lifetime.

As starting point, the description of the main channels selected for the project are in Figure 3 and Figure 4.

Figure 3: Dissemination and Communication Channels (1)

Figure 4: Dissemination and Communication Channels (2)

CHANNELS: Our channels included social media, press, web presence, newspapers, articles in journals, conferences and workshops, presentations, organizing or participating in events.

Table 3 outlines the original plan to approach the dissemination activities during the smashHit project's duration. The plan was generally followed, though with a change that many events have been held online and not onsite, due to the pandemic. This development has in particular directed our dissemination and communication efforts in the online spaces vs the offline spaces, and more efforts and resources were dedicated to the online digital objects production and online presence, and less to the offline dissemination (e.g. travel and printed materials).

Table 3: Activities

Communication Channel	When	What	How
Social media and website	M1-M36	Setting up the web and social media presence and keep them updated.	Developing the project's website, logo, flyer and poster templates and establishing a presence on social media channels namely <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Twitter, • LinkedIn, • Zenodo, • ResearchGate, • Spotify, • YouTube.
Scientific publications	M12-M36	Publications in journals and conferences.	Share innovations with the research community by publishing open access publications.
Events and conferences	M6-M36	Publicize the projects activities and results.	Participate in conferences and workshops to share results and discuss publications.
Press releases	M6-M36	Raise awareness about the smashHit project within different audiences.	Share results with the general public by targeting mainstream media, newspapers and newsletters.
Briefings and demonstrations	M24/M36	Publicize the project and encourage participation.	Publicize our good recommendation practise by realising briefing and commercial material to a wide range of stakeholders. Demonstrate the following Business Cases: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Services using integrated CPP and insurance data, • Services using integrated traffic, smart city and CPP data.
Marketing material	M3-M36	Non-scientific marketing material to acquaint the public with the project.	Prepare and share posters and flyers to users who do not have scientific background or do not read scientific publications on daily basis.
Blog posts	M6/M12/M18/M36	Release selected news to the stakeholders.	Create a network of interested stakeholders and share the latest news with them via a blog post (basis for a newsletter) every 6 months.

3 The Dissemination Activities and their Sustainability

The main objectives for the smashHit dissemination were to promote results, optimise exploitation, promote technology transfer and to support a continuous supply of new information. This was achieved with the help of various activities such as conference participation, collaborations and paper publications. An active online and offline presence were established to support the dissemination and communication even further. Collaboration between all partners is essential for the progress of this project.

According to Article 28, Section 28.1 from the Grant Agreement, all beneficiaries are obliged to exploit their results by:

- (a) Using them in further research activities (outside the action);
- (b) Developing, creating or marketing a product or process;
- (c) Creating and providing a service, or
- (d) Using them in standardisation activities.

Further, each beneficiary must — as soon as possible — ‘disseminate’ its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific publications (in any medium) (Article 29, Section 29.1 of the smashHit project agreement).

This section presents all dissemination activities, which are being undertaken, in separate subsections accordingly.

3.1 Project Repository

The smashHit employed project repositories that can be accessed by all partners as well as wider stakeholder groups. Namely, the repositories open only to project partners (such as Nextcloud⁴⁷), the partners’ repositories (e.g. publication databases of individual partners), and the repositories open for everyone (such as the project website, Github⁴⁸, Gitlab⁴⁹, Bitbucket⁵⁰).

smashHit has published the resulting papers from the focused workgroups in open access journals and conferences. The dissemination plan detailed the process for making scientific publications available online. smashHit uses Zenodo⁵¹ as a joint repository, which is part of the OpenAIRE⁵² service by the EC. In addition to this, individual partners also used repositories available at their respective institutions (e.g. archiving services, personal websites) to enhance the dissemination of the scientific publications.

AIM: To have an open access environment where smashHit partners could collaborate and share their progress.

3.2 Social Media and Professional Networks

The project partners have created and maintained the web and social media presence throughout the whole project. Table 4 and Table 5 present the social and professional channels that were currently set up and in use. A strategy for each social media platform is presented in Section 3.5.

AIM: To spread information about smashHit, its purpose, tasks and results thus raise awareness among the general public. Further, to target possible new stakeholders and collaborators.

Comparing to our original online dissemination plan (presented in D8.1 [1]), we have extended our reach to further platforms that facilitate distribution of audio and video content, namely, YouTube, Spotify and

⁴⁷ <https://nextcloud.com/>

⁴⁸ <https://github.com>

⁴⁹ <https://about.gitlab.com>

⁵⁰ <https://bitbucket.org>

⁵¹ <http://www.zenodo.org>

⁵² <https://www.openaire.eu/>

iTunes, for sharing podcasts. Production and distribution of such podcasts partly compensated for less exposures in terms of talks and meetings at events, which was caused by the COVID-19 pandemic.

Table 4: Social Media Platforms

Social Media	Link
Twitter	https://twitter.com/SmashhitP
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/smashhit
YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCnKnDSPB6fmn6kzKo716baA
Spotify	https://open.spotify.com/show/1pCNZEjLmwKmSuxt8Bks6L
iTunes	https://podcasts.apple.com/us/podcast/smashhits-podcast/id1546728595

Table 5: Professional Networks

Professional networks	Link
ResearchGate	https://www.researchgate.net/project/smashHit-Smart-Dispatcher-for-Secure-and-Controlled-Sharing-of-Distributed-Personal-and-Industrial-Data
Mendeley	https://www.mendeley.com/profiles/smashhit-horizon-/
smashHit Website	www.smashhit.eu

3.3 smashHit Logo

The project's logo (see Figure 5) is in use in the branding of the smashHit project (e.g. in the deliverable templates and on the social media accounts).

Figure 5: smashHit Logo

AIM: To create a recognizable brand for the project, promote brand recognition and develop curiosity among relevant stakeholders.

We believe that additional project “branding” can be driven partially by the initial design of the website. i.e. images, style-guides. Other design elements, colour pallet etc. contribute to the outlook of the smashHit blog.

3.4 smashHit Website

One of the main sources of news for our audiences is the official smashHit website. It contains a description about the project, contact information of each partner, updates on the project, achievements, publications and events in which partners participated. The website is updated systematically and acts as the submission platform for the future stakeholder engagement.

AIM: To act as a central information resource for stakeholders, the research community and people who are interested in the project.

The domain name: <https://www.smashhit.eu/> has been reserved and is used for the smashHit project.

The website has a structure allowing us to present the project outcomes such as deliverables and scientific publications, news, basic information about the project (as depicted in Figure 6).

Figure 6: smashHit Website

3.5 Social Media Channels of smashHit

Social media platforms such as Twitter⁵³ and LinkedIn⁵⁴ are the main tools for publicly presenting our results and keeping users informed with the progress of the smashHit project.

- **LinkedIn⁵⁴**
<https://www.linkedin.com/company/smashhit> (see also the image of the project profile on Figure 7). During the duration of the project, partners have been asked to provide the input about their progress and achievements together with short descriptions. Further, in order to reach wider audience and raise awareness, we repost relevant articles shared by others in our community thus assuring that the smashHit project stays active on the web.

We stayed active on LinkedIn by:

- having each partner regularly provide input for the posts, and re-posting these posts,
- engaging with others in the community and
- reposting relevant finding such as articles, events, news, software, videos.

⁵³ <https://twitter.com>

⁵⁴ <https://www.linkedin.com>

SmashHit - EU Project Content admin view

Home Products Content Analytics Activity 5

Start a post

Photo Video Poll Write article

Page posts Following Hashtags Employee posts Ads

Filter admin posts by: All

Get up to 160 more clicks by boosting this post. Boost

Posted by Ina O' Murchu · 10/6/2022 Pinned

SmashHit - EU Project
253 followers
3mo ·

We are pleased to inform you that our article "Automated GDPR Contract Compliance Verification Using Knowledge Graphs" has been published in Information as part of the Special Issue Knowledge Graph Technok ...see more

Automated GDPR Contract Compliance Verification

Figure 7: smashHit LinkedIn Page

- **Twitter**⁵³
<https://twitter.com/SmashhitP> (see also the image of the project profile on Figure 8)

In comparison to LinkedIn, which is aimed at professionals, Twitter provides a more diverse audience of people, which could be used as an advantage. Further, it is a dynamic platform and a source of news for many. Being present on Twitter would give the possibility to widely popularize smashHit among people from different backgrounds by reaching out to a wider more diverse audience. We use Twitter to:

- Post information about the project such as our mission and main goal.
- Engage with the research community by participating in conversations and adding comments.
- Attract possible collaborations.
- Raise awareness about smashHit.

With Twitter, we aim at presenting news, project results and keep the users updated about the progress of the project with the help of visual aims such as podcasts, video, images, tables and graphs. Further, call-to-action and hashtags are used to engage the users.

Further, we have extended our media presence for channels supporting the format of podcast, namely, **YouTube** (<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCnKnDSPB6fmn6kzKo716baA>),

Spotify (<https://open.spotify.com/show/1pCNZEjLmwKmSuxt8Bks6L>) and

iTunes (<https://podcasts.apple.com/us/podcast/smashhits-podcast/id1546728595>). Three dedicated podcasts containing interviews with project partners have been produced and distributed.

We use podcasts to:

- Explain what the project is working on in more detail.
- Communicate ongoing project work in an audio format, with the contents suitable for general audience and specialists interested in the topic.

Figure 9 is demonstrating the published podcasts and one of these channels, namely, Spotify.

Figure 8: smashHit Twitter Page

3.6 Traditional Media and Newspapers

Some examples of traditional media and newspapers that the smashHit consortium partners envisioned to contact for dissemination of the project were (some of these traditional media also have an online presence and the dissemination would be performed via the print and/or online channels - given the COVID-19 developments even more emphasis is being put on online channels):

International Newspapers:

- Scitech Europa⁵⁵

⁵⁵ <https://www.scitecheuropa.eu>

- The European⁵⁶
- Pc Welt⁵⁷
- Traffic Technology Today⁵⁸
- Weserkurier⁵⁹
- Wired⁶⁰

Figure 9: smashHit Spotify Page

- Business Insider⁶¹
- TechCrunch⁶²

Local Media and Newspapers:

⁵⁶ <https://the-european.eu>

⁵⁷ <https://www.pcwelt.de>

⁵⁸ <https://www.traffictechnologytoday.com>

⁵⁹ <https://www.weser-kurier.de>

⁶⁰ <https://www.wired.com>

⁶¹ <https://www.businessinsider.com>

⁶² <https://techcrunch.com>

- Tiroler Tageszeitung⁶³
- Austria Innovative⁶⁴
- Computer Bild⁶⁵
- IT Now⁶⁶
- TreeGic Magazine⁶⁷
- Weser Kurier⁶⁸

The initial plan of using the traditional media was changed due to COVID-19. This is because of online media, such as podcast and spotify was increased significantly due to COVID-19.

3.7 Blog Posts

A blog containing the latest information about the project is being developed with specializing tools such as MailChimp⁶⁹ and Blogger⁷⁰ and updated regularly. The blog posts would deliver its message in a clear and attractive manner. At least 4 blog posts have been planned to be created. We believe that printed media is not within the main spirit of this project, nor it is efficient and easy to manage, thus most of the communication would be digital.

AIM: Create a network of interested parties around the project, which would help share results, publicise calls and raise awareness.

The blog posts have been published persistently. The published blog posts are presented in Table 6. Besides, we have outperformed the initial plan by producing in total eleven blog posts, four blog posts about own podcasts, and in addition, two calls for participation in surveys (conducted at the end of 2020, facilitating the data collection for the deliverables of other workpackages, see: <https://smashhit.eu/newsroom/>).

Table 6: smashHit Blog Post Planning and Execution

Blog Post	Release Date	Title	Topics	Created By
1	August 2020	smashHit Podcast 1: Data Consent With ATB's Ana Correia	Data transparency and consent	ATB
2	September 2020	The smashHit Project: general information, objectives and partners.	Purpose, Strategy, Aims and Objectives.	All
3	October 2020	Podcast 2: Data Consent With Victor Corral (ATOS)	Data transparency and consent	ATOS
4	March 2021	Podcast 3: Connected Car Data with Nick Walker Of LexisNexis Risk Solutions	Insurance BC	LN

⁶³ <https://www.tt.com>

⁶⁴ <https://www.austriainnovativ.at>

⁶⁵ <http://computerbild.de>

⁶⁶ <https://www.bcs.org/membership/become-a-member/itnow/>

⁶⁷ <https://www.magzter.com/MX/TreeGic-Magazine/TreeGic-Magazine/Technology/>

⁶⁸ <https://www.weser-kurier.de/bremen.html>

⁶⁹ <https://mailchimp.com>

⁷⁰ <https://www.blogger.com>

Blog Post	Release Date	Title	Topics	Created By
5	May 2021	The smashHit Business Cases 1 and 2: specifications, details and prototype	CPP and Insurance Data Integration, Traffic, Smart City and CPP Data Integration.	VW, LN, FVH
6	June 2021	Podcast 4: Forum Virium & Smart Cities Use Case	Smart City BC	FVH
7	February 2022	Data Use Traceability and Fingerprinting	Traceability and Fingerprinting Approaches, Data Privacy.	LUH
8	March 2022	Transposing Data Protection Requirements into Technical and Organisational Measures: The smashHit Approach	Cyber security, privacy	LUH
9	October 2022	smashHit's Closing Event at EBDVF	Introducing the final event	UIBK
10	November 2022	The smashHit session at the EBDVF2022 was a success!	Final event	ATB
11	December 2022	Different Steps of GPS Trajectory Watermarking	GPS Data Re-identification, Data ownership	UBO, LUH

3.8 Dissemination in EU technology platforms, co-operations with EU projects

The smashHit project communicates and disseminates to other EU technology platforms and projects, as well as thematic platforms (e.g. smart city platforms).

Cooperation with the following platforms is aimed at and/or already carried out:

- **BDVA⁷¹**: our solution for data driven digital transformations could contribute to the policy development and technology ramification supported by the BDVA.
- **NESSI⁷²**: smashHit will include software development and platforms such as NESSI could provide valuable inputs about research and technology matters related to the software domain.

The cooperation with other EU projects that was carried out as follows:

- **CampaNeo**: the smashHitCore ontology (or the semantic models), one of the core components of the smashHit project, reused ontology from the CampaNeo project.
- **DALICC²³**: smashHit is employing the project's outcomes in the area of semantic content and data licensing [8], and also collaborates with the other follow up activities of the DALICC project.
- **Cross-CPP**: since ATB is the coordinator of Cross-CPP having other partners in common (TOG, ATOS and VW), and Cross-CPP that is dealing with CPP data offered in a Marketplace to be used in cross-sectorial services, the topic is quite relevant for the smashHit project. The Cross-CPP project's knowledge was applied to the smashHit project, such as for the security and privacy component.

⁷¹ <http://www.bdva.eu>

⁷² <http://www.nessi-europe.com/default.aspx?page=home>

- **I3-MARKET⁷³**: this project addresses the growing demand for a single European Data Market Economy by innovating marketplace platforms, demonstrating with industrial implementations that the data economy growth is possible. The i3-MARKET proposal provides technologies for trustworthy (secure and reliable) data-driven collaboration and federation of existing and new future marketplace platforms. Special attention is on industrial data and particularly on sensitive commercial data assets from both SMEs to large industrial corporations. ATOS is part of these 14 consortium partners by providing the AGORA solution as a pilot for the automotive sector. Therefore, the synergies and collaboration between I3-MARKET and smashHit could leverage networking opportunities and knowledge exchange between both projects.
- **TRUSTS (Trusted Secure Data Sharing Space)**: the project builds on two large national data market projects and wants to allow the integration of multiple platform, which work under different jurisdictions. The developed data-sharing platform aims to be the basis for secure, trustworthy and GDPR-compliant data exchanges. The focus of this project is on the integration and interoperability of different (national) data markets. L3S is the lead and coordinator of the consortium consisting of 17 partners. L3S is exchanging information between the smashHit and the TRUSTS project to identify synergies and maximise both project impacts. We also participated and presented smashHit at a workshop organised by the project in May in Vienna, as a position paper and presentation.
- **DataVaults⁷⁴**: the project aims to address issues such as data privacy, ethics and intellectual property rights by allowing users to be in control of their data and with who it is shared. The DataVaults framework and platform focuses on personal data and its representation as a multidimensional ecosystem that is regulated by smart contracts. Both DataVaults and smashHit are closely related when it comes to the topics of data protection and user rights. As being a part of the 17 partners involved in the DataVaults project, ATOS could help establish future collaboration with smashHit, which could be mutually beneficial.
- **MyDataShare⁷⁵**: MyDataShare is a human-centric approach to personal data management. MyDataShare (a MyData operator platform), is available globally for all entities and organisations in need of a human-centric and transparent tool to facilitate their needs for secondary-use personal data collection, sharing and access, as defined in the global MyData Principles. Forum Virium and Infotripla have lead the communication and first alignment attempts between both MyDataShare and smashHit.
- **EU Hubs 4 Data⁷⁶ (EUH4D)**: The EU-funded EUHubs4Data project is building a European federation of Data Innovation Hubs based on existing key players in this area and connecting with data incubators and platforms, SME networks, AI communities, skills and training organisations and open data repositories. The collaboration was lead by ATB and ATOS but involved all RTD partners. The collaboration's goal is to make the smashHit results public by updating EUH4D catalogue services. EUH4D catalogue services collect information about projects and project outcomes.
- **Data Spaces Support Centre**: The "Data Spaces for Europe" project is setting up and operate a Data Spaces Support Centre, as described in the Digital Europe Programme, to operationalize the European Strategy for Data. This Support Centre will facilitate common data spaces that collectively create an interoperable data sharing environment, to enable data reuse within and across sectors, fully respecting EU values, and contributing to the European economy and society. The project brings together associations and industry players, including SMEs, regulators, and digital innovation hubs, to foster the creation of data spaces. The collaboration was set up in advance of the EBDVF 2022 to see how smashHit can contribute with its building blocks⁷⁷.

3.9 Events, Conferences and Journals

Participation in talks, panel discussions, conferences and workshops is essential for the dissemination of the smashHit project. Further, smashHit also aims at publishing in various journals:

⁷³ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/871754/es>

⁷⁴ <https://www.datavaults.eu>

⁷⁵ <https://www.mydatashare.com>

⁷⁶ <https://euhubs4data.eu>

⁷⁷ <https://dssc.eu/>

- Publishing in **open access journals**, which would make the data and content available immediately.
- **Publishing via the “gold” route**, whereby authors pay a fee to publish material as open access immediately. This is usually offered by most of the high-level journals and would be seen as a potential direct cost in the smashHit budget.
- **Publishing via the “green” route**. Materials would be stored in a disciplinary, institutional or public repository (Section 3.1) and would be available as open access after a specific embargo period.

AIM: To publicise the project and share results with the research communities and encourage involvement which could lead to future collaborations. Further, create a multi-disciplinary innovation community to contribute to the project.

A detailed and complete overview of events at which smashHit was presented by consortium members is provided in the data appendix file for this deliverable ⁷⁸ [9]. The attended events with the project presentation so far are as follows.

Events where partners participated in 2020:

- BDV PPP Summit (ATOS)
- EBDVF 2020 (ATOS)
- BDV PPP GOING VIRTUAL – DATA PLATFORM WEBINARS (ATB)
- Big Data PPP Mixed Data Platforms: “B2B and B2C together” (ATB)
- Using the Connected Car’s Digital Data in the Real World (ATB, LNRS)
- Internal meeting (UIBK)
- NODES 2020 Neo4j Online Developer Expo and Summit (UIBK)
- SEMIC Conference 2020 (LUH, UBO)
- Profiles workshop (LUH, UBO)
- Symposium Intelligente Mobilität (LUH)
- Internal meeting – 2 times (VW)
- BDVA Standards Workshop (TOG)
- Making Data Useful Conference (TOG)
- H2020 Project Information Exchange (TOG, VW, ATB)
- Automotive Edge Hackathon (VW)
- Hackathon presentation (VW)
- Dissertation (LUH)

Events where partners participated in 2021:

- Big Data and Security (BDS) Internal Innovation workshop (ATOS)
- BDVA/DAIRO Activity Group meeting 43, 18th - 19th of March, SESSION 2: Two-sided/Multi-sided aspects of data platforms (ATB)
- Colloquium on data science and artificial intelligence (UIBK)
- GISRUK Online Seminar Series 2021 (UBO, LUH)
- 2021 Oil and Gas High Performance Computing Conference (UIBK)
- Data Week 2021 Workshop (ATB)
- Open Digital Standards Conference (TOG)
- Internal meeting – 3 times (VW)
- European Semantic Web Conference – 2 presentations (UIBK)
- International Journal of Geo-Information: Spatial Issue on Spatio-Temporal Models and Geo-Technologies (UBO, LUH)
- IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Transportation ITSC2021 (UBO, LUH)
- International Conference on Information and Knowledge Management (CIKM '21) (UBIO, LUH)
- DLR Open Search Kolloquium (UBO)
- PhD thesis and project presentation at Wageningen University (UIBK)
- ITS World Congress 2021 (INFT)
- EBDVF 2021 (ATOS)

⁷⁸ Detailed list of smashHit events and publications, Excel sheet, [Online]. Available as a dataset associated with this deliverable at: <https://smashhit.eu/deliverables>

Events where partners participated in 2022:

- The Web Conference 2022 (UBO, LUH)
- ACM SIGKDD Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining 2022 (UBO, LUH)
- ACM SIGSPATIAL 2022 (UBO, LUH)
- TRUSTS Workshop 2022, Vienna (UIBK)
- The Knowledge Graph Conference 2022, New York (UIBK, online presentation)
- Orientation Week 2022 (UBO)
- Summer School on Cryptography 2022 (UBO, LUH)
- KIRAHub event 2022 (INFT)
- Tampere Smart City Week 2022 (INFT)
- Mydata 2022 (INFT, FVH)
- Liikenteestä liiketoimintaa (Making transport a business, Conference 2022 (INFT)
- Seminar at Leiden University, online (UIBK)
- [EBDVF 2022](#) with a project both, own project session and participation in an overview session (all consortium partners)
- Towards FAIR Data Management postgraduate course, Wageningen (UIBK)
- 2 Dissertation (UIBK) (Anelia Kurteva : “Making Sense of Consent with Knowledge Graphs”, 2022. and Sven Rasmusen: “Increasing Trust and Engagement in the Age of GDPR: A Digital Contracting Tool Supported by Knowledge Graphs”, 2022)

For further potential events and publication venues where the project could participate (according to the plan), see Section 3.9 of the project’s D8.1 [1].

The communication and dissemination mention all the project’s partners in the communication and dissemination connections whenever possible, as it gives visibility to partner organizations and enhances long term impact beyond the EU-project lifetime. Naturally, the project also follows the Horizon 2020 Communication guidelines⁷⁹, and will be explicitly acknowledging the EU funding in the communication⁸⁰.

3.10 Final Exhibition

In order to display and present the results of smashHit, a final project event was organized. It included European policy makers, high-profile association representatives, major research institutions, major industry bodies and intermediaries, regulatory bodies at national and European levels. The chosen event, within which the final smashHit project event was embedded, was the European Big Data Value Forum 2022 (EBDVF22) held in Prague on 21-23 November, 2022.

The final exhibition event had around 400 participants (thus exceeding the goal to have at least 100 high level participants).

AIM: To ensure that potential stakeholders are aware of the smashHit project’s contributions and to demonstrate their value. Most of all, to publicise the project’s results and recommendations to further support the data value chain.

The participation in the event was 3 fold:

- Project booth,
- Participation in the session “Lessons learnt from Data Platforms projects”,
- Organisation of a project session with the title “An Innovative Approach to Compliant Consent”.

In the smashHit’s final event there was a chance to interact and discuss in-person with the conference attendees at our booth. On top of that, we also had a scheduled in the main EBDVF programme session “An Innovative Approach to Compliant Consent” with a presentation followed by a panel discussion (see Figure 10).

⁷⁹ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/acknowledge-funding_en.htm

⁸⁰ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/communication_en.htm

Onsite communication materials, namely, project flyer, has been distributed to every registered EBDVF participant (in the conference bag).

Figure 10: EBDVF session “An Innovative Approach to Compliant Consent”

The presentation was focused on the smashHit platform and also addressing the important questions such as:

- The Market Challenge - what are we trying to solve?
- The Impact of Solving the Challenges - what does the challenge mean?
- The building blocks of the solution - how we solved the challenge?
- The future plan - what do we plan next?

After the presentation, the panel discussion was comprised of Nick Walker (LN), Pekka Koponen (FVH), Dr. Mohammed Al-Rifai (VW), Kimmo Rossi (European Commission), Ivan Carrillo (ATOS), and it was moderated by Christian Wolff (ATB).

The event was announced under our blog post <https://smashhit.eu/smashhits-closing-event-at-ebdvf/> and it was streamed live in our youtube channel. The video can be found on demand at the following link: <https://youtu.be/2Jn5nHfbQ3l>.

As mentioned in the blog post reflecting the final event <https://smashhit.eu/the-smashhit-session-at-the-ebdvf2022-was-a-success/>, we quote it here:

“During the discussion we had the possibility to dive deeper into the topics raised in the presentation and by the audience, such as current consent barriers for data sharing, and ongoing and potential standardisation activities for smashHit components. Kimmo Rossi also gave interesting insights on ongoing activities in the consent and data spaces field from the European Commission’s point of view.”

As mentioned in the blog post the event was a success, in which we had a number of questions also from the participants on the topic of data sharing, consent and the synergy with data markets.

3.11 Communication Material

Further, the project has the project flyer and poster template. These can be and are shared online through the smashHit social media channels, and on workshops and conferences.

Figure 11 presents the design of the smashHit poster, whereas Figure 12 presents the design of the smashHit flyer. The poster was used in the booth of the final event, and the flyer was put to the participants’ bags. The flyers’ purpose was to serve as a teaser, in order to attract as many participants as possible to our booth and to our session.

In the event itself, we had printed a number of smashHit's Concept white papers⁸¹ at our booths, which we used as additional material for the booth visitors in case we needed to go deeper into the technical parts.

AIM: To act as a central information resource for stakeholders interested in the project and to present the smashHit project and its purpose.

3.12 Demonstrators' Videos

Dissemination activities were supported by demonstrating or representing business cases BC1 and BC2 through videos. To present BC1 to the outside world there were 3 videos were made and published on the smashHit website (see Table 7). There were 2 videos regarding BC2 available online (see Table 8).

Table 7: Demonstrator Videos BC1 (D6.5)

No	Title	Link
1	Demonstrator of UC1.1 - LexisNexis Consent Management Platform	https://vimeo.com/785239596/af16603a53
2a	Demonstrator of UC1.2 - Data Traceability	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=awjAyXuopBI
2b	Demonstrator of UC1.2 - Data Traceability	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HZK7XXNlxn4

Table 8: Demonstrator Videos BC2 (D7.5)

No	Title	Link
1	City Feedback App: creating a more pleasant city with feedback	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YTSMqrQtviM
2	Safer streets for pedestrians – smart corner tested in Helsinki in smashHit project	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CdHRJG4QBKc

⁸¹ https://smashhit.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/WHITE-PAPER-smashHit_concept_v07.pdf

A SMART DISPATCHER FOR THE SECURED & CONTROLLED EXCHANGE OF PERSONAL AND INDUSTRIAL DATA

HIGHLIGHTS

Secure

GDPR Compliance

Trust & Transparency

BACKBONE OF SMASHHIT

Follow us on social:

AUTOMATED CONTRACTING

One-Click consumer consent management

TRACEABLE DATA USAGE

Digital watermark / fingerprint for checking data authenticity

BUSINESS CASES

INTELLIGENT USE OF VEHICLE DATA

- New insurance models, such as mileage-based vehicle insurance
- Benefit from safe driving behavior without the need for any additional hardware
- Control of transmitted data

SMART CITY HELSINKI

- Ensuring MyData principles in data sharing
- More accurate and real-time data about the city traffic
- Involving citizens in producing data and benefiting from sharing it

Figure 11: smashHit Poster

ARCHITECTURE OF THE AUTOMATED GDPR COMPLIANCE VERIFICATION TOOL ¹

SEMANTIC REPRESENTATION OF CONTRACTS ²

AUTOMATED GDPR COMPLIANCE VERIFICATION TOOL FUNCTIONALITIES & FEATURES:

- Scalable automated GDPR compliance verification for both consent and contract.
- Data protection by design principles have been adopted to ensure the safety of the data.
- Use of Next Generation Access Control (NGAC) as a part of security and privacy module for granular management of consent.
- Interoperability of consent and contracts using the Knowledge Graphs (KGs) via relationships between concepts.
- Semi-automatic consent status update, namely, consent granting and revocation.

TRACEABILITY FUNCTIONALITIES & FEATURES:

- Enable transparency of data sharing by adopting data traces
- Facilitate tracing data flows by hashing, fingerprinting, and watermarking
- Support data re-identification and ownership verification in case of data breaches
- Make the data recognizable under adversarial modifications (attacks)

Data use traceability workflow

Example scenario for data re-identification

Attack examples

¹ Ohtani, T.B., Kurita, A., Odagiri, R., Uehara, S., Kawai, K. and Fumoto, A., 2022. Data Protection by Design Tool for Automated GDPR Compliance Verification Based on Generatively Induced Informal Consent Semantics. 2022. p. 764.

² Tsujita, A., Kurita, A., Ohtani, T., A. Hironaka, and Fumoto, A., 2022. Automated GDPR Contract Compliance Verification Using Knowledge Graphs. Information, 13(10), p. 447.

A SMART DISPATCHER FOR THE SECURED & CONTROLLED EXCHANGE OF PERSONAL AND INDUSTRIAL DATA

smashHit

CONSENT CERTIFICATION PROCESS

1. Data subject identity registration
2. Consent request generation
3. Consent request presentation
4. Consent request confirmation
5. Consent confirmation
6. Consent confirmation
7. Signature
8. Consent confirmation
9. Consent confirmation

BUSINESS CASES

INTELLIGENT USE OF VEHICLE DATA

- New insurance models, such as mileage-based vehicle insurance
- Benefit from safe driving behavior without the need for any additional hardware
- Control of transmitted data

SMART CITY HELSINKI

- Receive real time route recommendations in vehicle
- Timely information on traffic jams
- Sensor data, such as temperature or air quality

Come visit us in our booth No 10 and in the session:

An Innovative Approach to Compliant Consent
November 22, 2022 - 17:00 - 18:00
Aplaus room

FUNDED BY:
 HORIZON 2020 EUROPEAN UNION FUNDING FOR RESEARCH & INNOVATION NO. 871477

Figure 12: smashHit flyer (version for the final event at EBDVF 2022)

4 Dissemination and Communication Reporting

The dissemination and communication continue to develop though the whole span of the smashHit project. All partners contribute to the dissemination by sharing their progress on social media, attend events, publish in journals, and appear in media and local newspapers. A reporting template with specific metrics is used for monitoring partners' contributions through the whole project's timeline, specifically, summarising events and publications. For the first half of the project, the filled out report from all partners is available as Excel file, containing all the details [9].

4.1 Success Metrics

Here, we define the targeted key performance metrics for our different dissemination activities, and analyse how they are met so far. Each table below specifies what KPIs are expected to be met with regards to the corresponding activities. The provided values would be used as a guideline when evaluating the progress of the project and could fluctuate.

The KPI's are combined across the full consortium and assuming a 36-month duration. Our existing insights and web resources attain these numbers. We use IP tracking so we can see at an organisational / company level – metrics that may be better to look at. For example, which and how many visitors we cover rather than how many sessions we observe, etc.

Dissemination of the project includes participation in various events, newsletters, scientific publications, etc. An overview of all desired KPIs are described in Table 9. Table 10 provide more detailed success metrics that are activity based.

Table 9: Overall Dissemination and Communication smashHit KPIs

Activity	Success Rate
Use case and technology project open sessions	KPI: More than 50 ecosystem members attending.
Participation in workshops, conferences and other international events	KPI: More than 10 events.
Briefings and demonstrations at third-party events	KPI: Attend more than 20 such events where the number of stakeholders is more than 1000.
Newsletters	KPI: At least 4.
Scientific publications	KPI: 3-5 and technical contributions.
Final Exhibition	KPI: >100 high-level participants in the final event.

The project's website is one of the main tools for popularization of the smashHit project and provides the latest news and discoveries. It may be the core platform for information, but we use social media, press releases, conferences etc. to drive traffic to it. Desired KPIs are presented in Table 9 We also highlight with colour where we currently are in terms of achievement of these KPIs.

Number of sessions represents a group of user interactions with our website that takes place within a given time frame.

Number of page views identifies the number of individual users who visited the website.

Number of unique views is the number of the unique users that click on a tracking link of a campaign⁸².

Number of followers measures the number of users who decided to follow smashHit on social media.

⁸² <https://www.similarweb.com/corp/blog/unique-visitors/>

Table 10: Website Metrics

Project's Website (2020-2022)	Poor	Good	Excellent
Number of sessions	<2,000	2,000-7,000	7,000+
Number of page views	<10,000	10,000-15,000	15,000+
Number of unique visitors	<3,000	3,000-7,000	7,000+

The actual figures of the performance of the smashHit website are presented in Figure 13 respectively. Note that the Google Analytics traffic tracker has been set on the website only in May 2020, so the actual figures are slightly larger. Figure 14 shows the audience overview, showing statistics such as page views and sessions as well as the location from which the website has been accessed. As can be seen from Figure 13, the majority of our viewers are from the EU, the region we are mostly focused on. Moreover, we can also see the global access from other regions, such as America, Asia, and Africa. This shows the global interest in our work, which is very important because it will increase the adaptability of our work (or findings), not only at the EU level but also on the global level. Moreover, the language statistics in Figure 13 show further diversity among the users. This shows that our website has not been accessed just from one country within the EU, but that there is diversity. Similarly, Figure 14 shows an overview of the user's behaviour. Figure 14 demonstrates that all aspects of our website, including news and publications, are of interest to users. This demonstrates that our efforts to disseminate our work through the creation of content such as news, white papers, and scientific publications have been successful. On the other hand, Figure 15 shows the information about the traffic channels, i.e., how users reached our website. As can be observed from Figure 15, 34.5% of our traffic is from searches via search engines like Google, demonstrating the interest in our work. Furthermore, this also supports the diversity of the access, which was shown in Figure 12.

Figure 13: smashHit Website Audience Overview (Status: December 6, 2022)

With regard to our KPI metrics, as of the date of this deliverable (i.e., December 6, 2022), we currently have 4,274 sessions, 13,530 page views, and 9,498 unique page views or unique visitors presented in Figure 15. This falls under the category of the good and excellent and has been highlighted accordingly in Table 11.

Figure 14: smashHit Website Audience Behaviour Overview (Status: December 6, 2022)

Google Analytics Acquisition Overview

Figure 15: smashHit Website Traffic Acquisition Overview (Status: December 6, 2022)

Social Media such as Twitter and LinkedIn were planned to meet the following metrics (Table 11). Here, we also highlight with colour where we currently are in terms of achievement of these KPIs. The specified metrics are for the whole duration of the project. Successful presence on Twitter and LinkedIn is measured by keeping track of the new followers, likes and posts. Each partner has contributed to this by posting and resharing featured posts. As it can be seen from the Table 10, the only KPI that has 'Poor' evaluation are Twitter followers, and this is due to the fact that the target number of 500 was set as too ambitious in the first place, given the typical audience that is present on Twitter (the carried out dissemination was very professional audience oriented, and this has been an intentional choice made while executing the dissemination plan). The visibility of the Twitter content was still in planned good and excellent ranges, with many people seeing and interacting the content, even when not being a follower of the project.

Table 11: Social Media Metrics

Social Media	Poor	Good	Excellent
Twitter followers	<500	500-800	800+
Twitter posts	<100	100-200	200+
Twitter likes	<300	300-600	600+
Twitter post shares	<100	100-200	200+

Social Media	Poor	Good	Excellent
LinkedIn followers	<150	150-250	250+
LinkedIn posts	<100	100-200	200+
LinkedIn likes	<300	300-600	600+
LinkedIn post shares	<100	100-200	200+

Twitter:

The SmashHit Twitter profile is accessible at www.twitter.com/smashhitP. As of the date of writing for this deliverable, there are currently **225** twitter followers, over **660** tweets (including **242** retweets). As of now, the number of likes is more than **450**.

In Figure 16, you can see the recent activity of the smashHit twitter account.

Figure 16: Twitter analytics on the last 28 day period, showing top tweets.

LinkedIn

The smashHit LinkedIn profile is accessible at <https://www.linkedin.com/company/smashhit>. As of the date of writing for this deliverable, December, 2022, there are currently **252** smashHit LinkedIn followers, over 200 posts, and 700 post likes. The LinkedIn contents can be accessed using the smashHit LinkedIn public profile. Figure 17 shows the overall impressions and highlights from December 2021 to December 2022.

Figure 17: smashHit – LinkedIn Impressions for December 2021-December 2022 (status: December 7, 2022)

Similarly, Figure 18 show the access to smashHit LinkedIn contents based on the job functions, the company size the individuals are working for, and their seniority levels. We can clearly observe from Figure 18 that smashHit's LinkedIn contents have reached a wide audience with respect to the levels of seniority and also the company size. Importantly, our work attracted individuals with decision-making authority, such as directors, vice presidents, and owners, as can be observed in Figure 20. In a similar manner, with respect to company size, we have reached companies of all sizes—small, medium, and large—with more than 10,000 employees. Our work on this project is more focused on research and innovation. So, ideally, one would expect more people from the research or to reach more scientists. From Figure 18, we can observe that we have reached more people doing research via LinkedIn. Moreover, from Figure 18, we can observe the diverse audience that we have reached, including people from academia, business, engineering, and information technology.

With respect to our KPI, with LinkedIn, we stand between good and excellent. We are in an excellent range for LinkedIn posts, likes and followers. For post re-shares and the number of followers, we are in a good range.

Figure 18: smashHit – Identification of the individuals who accessed the smashHit LinkedIn contents based on their job functions.

Figure 19: smashHit – Identification of individuals who accessed smashHit LinkedIn content based on the size of their respective companies

Figure 20: smashHit – Identification of individuals who accessed smashHit LinkedIn content based on their seniority level

For podcasts, the consumption/downloads of the produced content in total (on YouTube, Spotify, iTunes) have been amounting to over 300 times from November 2020 to December 2022, i.e., end of project.

As visible from the Excel sheet with the involvement with events and statistics from online media, the project is already predominantly in the “Good” and sometimes in the “Excellent” range w.r.t. the targeted KPIs. In all following tables, we highlight with a background colour the thresholds that have been already achieved as of now.

Specific metrics about media presence for the whole duration of the project are defined in Table 11 while in Table 12 we define KPIs for attending conferences (EU and international) and events (public events, workshops, conferences) during the lifespan of the project.

Table 12: Media Communication and Newsletters Metrics

Media Communication and Newsletters	Poor	Good	Excellent
Number of media articles mentioning smashHit	<10	10-20	20+
Number of newsletters circulated	<4	4-8	8+

This numbers presented in Table 13 are valid for the situation at the moment of initial planning. Taking into account the COVID-19 some of these events would be organised online thus KPI metrics could be different.

The key newsletters appearances are as follows (detailed and further information is in the data appendix [9]).

Key newsletters and media appearances by the partners in 2020:

- ATOS Research and Innovation (ARI) Newsletter (ATOS)
- Kysely henkilötietojen hyödyntämisestä (FVH)
- Consumer content & data security survey (FVH)
- Secure data sharing: the SmashHit project (FVH)

- Survey for data consumers and Survey for Data Providers (ATOS, UIBK as smashHit project newsletter)

Key newsletters and media appearances by the partners in 2021:

- Enabling Interpretability in Smart Cities With Knowledge Graphs: Towards a Better Modelling of Consent (UIBK at IEEE Smart Cities eNewsletter)
- SmashHit-hankkeelta Innovaatiokonsepti (FVH)

Key newsletters and media appearances by the partners in 2022:

- Forum Virium Newsletter (FVH)
- ATOS Research and Innovation (ARI) Newsletter (ATOS)

Additionally, the partners have been delivering dedicated webpages, blog and social media posts on various channels [9].

Table 13: Conference and Events Metrics

Conference Events	and	Poor	Good	Excellent
Number of conferences and workshops where smashHit is presented	where is	<10	10-20	20+
Number of third-party events with audience >1000		<20	20-30	30+

Naturally due to pandemics, participation in very large physical events is hindered, but is partly replaced by events with online participation and increased presence on social media platforms.

Publications in journals will help popularize the project and share our achievements with the academia and public. KPIs are shown in Table 14.

Table 14: Publications Metrics

Publications	Poor	Good	Excellent
Number of published papers	<5	5-10	10+

As visible from the Excel sheet associated with this deliverable [9] and the tables of this section, the project is already in the “Excellent” range w.r.t. the publication metrics. The accepted academic publications are at high profile competitive venues, such as in *Semantic Web* journal, European Semantic Web Conference, *International Journal of Geo-Information*. The up to date scientific publications stemming from the project are as follows:

1. Tauqeer, A., Kurteva, A., Chhetri, T.R., Ahmeti, A. and Fensel, A., 2022. Automated GDPR Contract Compliance Verification Using Knowledge Graphs. *Information*, 13(10), p.447.
2. Chhetri, T.R., Kurteva, A., DeLong, R.J., Hilscher, R., Korte, K. and Fensel, A., 2022. Data Protection by Design Tool for Automated GDPR Compliance Verification Based on Semantically Modeled Informed Consent. *Sensors*, 22(7), p.2763.
3. Kurteva A., Chhetri T.R., Pandit H.J., Fensel A. (2021). "Consent through the lens of semantics: state of the art survey and best practices". *Semantic Web – Interoperability, Usability, Applicability - an IOS Press Journal*, in press.

4. Tempelmeier N., Feuerhake U., Wage O., Demidova E. "Mining Topological Dependencies of Recurrent Congestion in Road Networks". *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*. 2021; 10(4):248.
5. Bless C., Dötlinger L., Kaltschmid M., Reiter M., Kurteva A., Roa-Valverde A.J, Fensel, A. (2021). "Raising Awareness of Data Sharing Consent Through Knowledge Graph Visualisation". In *Proceedings of the 17th International Conference on Semantic Systems (SEMANTICS 2021)*, IOS Press in Studies on the Semantic Web.
6. Chhetri T.R. (2021). "Improving Decision Making using Semantic Web Technologies". In *Proceedings of European Semantic Web Conference (ESWC 2021) PhD Symposium*, Lecture Notes in Computer Science 12739, Springer.
7. Dadwal, R., Funke, T. and Demidova, E., 2021, September. An Adaptive Clustering Approach for Accident Prediction. In *2021 IEEE International Intelligent Transportation Systems Conference (ITSC)* (pp. 1405-1411). IEEE.
8. Kurteva A. (2021). "Implementing Informed Consent with Knowledge Graphs". In *Proceedings of European Semantic Web Conference (ESWC 2021) PhD Symposium*, Lecture Notes in Computer Science 12739, Springer.
9. Sao, A., Tempelmeier, N. and Demidova, E., 2021, September. Deep Information Fusion for Electric Vehicle Charging Station Occupancy Forecasting. In *2021 IEEE International Intelligent Transportation Systems Conference (ITSC)* (pp. 3328-3333). IEEE.
10. Gottschalk, S. and Demidova, E., 2022. Tab2KG: Semantic table interpretation with lightweight semantic profiles. *Semantic Web*, (Preprint), pp.1-27.
11. Tempelmeier N., Demidova E. (2022). "Attention-Based Vandalism Detection in OpenStreetMap". In *Proceedings of the ACM Web Conference 2022*. ACM.
12. Von Wahl L., Tempelmeier N., Sao A., Demidova E. (2022). "Reinforcement Learning-based Placement of Charging Stations in Urban Road Networks". In *Proceedings of the 28th ACM SIGKDD Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*. ACM
13. Dadwal R., Funke T., Nüsken M., Demidova E. (2022). "W-Trace: Robust and Effective Watermarking for GPS Trajectories". In *Proceedings of the 30th International Conference on Advances in Geographic Information Systems*. ACM
14. Rasmusen, S. C., Penz, M., Widauer, S., Nako, P., Kurteva, A., Roa-Valverde, A., & Fensel, A. (2022). Raising Consent Awareness With Gamification and Knowledge Graphs: An Automotive Use Case. *International Journal on Semantic Web and Information Systems (IJSWIS)*, 18(1), 1-21. DOI: 10.4018/IJSWIS.300820.

Moreover, two doctoral and one master dissertation connected with the project has been defended:

- a. Thorben Funke (LUH): "Analyzing and Predicting Material Flow Networks Using Stochastic Block Models and Statistical Graph Embeddings", 2020.
- b. Anelia Kurteva (UIBK): "Making Sense of Consent with Knowledge Graphs", 2022.
- c. Sven Rasmusen: "Increasing Trust and Engagement in the Age of GDPR: A Digital Contracting Tool Supported by Knowledge Graphs", 2022

Furthermore, the Excel sheet provides the information about the publications that are currently either submitted or under review. Additionally, the Excel sheet also provides information about the list of the publications that are in progress, showing exploitation of the project beyond scientific results. However, one should note that the publications in preparations might change in terms of the titles. Some of the publications are listed below (only titles, for details check Excel sheet):

- a. Managing Data Protection Compliance through Maturity Models: A Primer
- b. A semantic-based privacy-aware framework for interoperable, accurate, and quality IoT data sharing
- c. What is in Your Cookie Box? Explaining Ingredients of Web Cookies with Knowledge Graphs
- d. The smashHitCore ontology for GDPR-compliant data sharing in smart cities
- e. Raising Consent Awareness With Gamification and Knowledge Graphs: An Automotive Use Case

4.2 Changes in the Plan and its Execution due to COVID-19

All partners in the smashHit project acknowledged the COVID-19 virus circumstances and their likely implications on the communication and dissemination of the project. smashHit followed its communication and dissemination activities as planned, with the needed adjustments (more of online than offline communication, in particular).

The conditions due to COVID-19 did not allow face-to-face meetings, thus some of the planned briefings and presentations carried out by the smashHit's partners were done online instead. This was achieved with the help of online communication tools such as WebEx⁸³, Zoom⁸⁴ or Skype⁸⁵. Presentations at large industrial events became possible again at a later point of time in the project, and in this case, they were made then. When it comes to the research and educational activities of the project, the production of research papers and teaching has been affected less, as submissions to scientific journals and conferences are typically done online, and the same holds meanwhile for teaching. Further, most of the scientific conferences had gone into the online mode or got postponed. To cover the possible gaps in the dissemination and communication, all partners aimed at engaging more in alternative channels e.g. establishing a stronger social media presence on Twitter, LinkedIn and on the smashHit's personal and partner's websites in order to continue the communication and dissemination of the project. Additional efforts have been placed into production of further, additional to the initial plan material, such as podcasts, and presence at the corresponding relevant platforms (such as YouTube, Spotify, iTunes) and dissemination there. Depending on the state of the pandemic situation, events and activities were discussed and changes in this plan were made accordingly to ensure the activity level similar to the planned one.

⁸³ <https://www.webex.com>

⁸⁴ <https://zoom.us>

⁸⁵ <https://www.skype.com/bg/>

5 Conclusions

This document presents the dissemination and communication report (M36) for the smashHit Horizon 2020 EU project. The communication and dissemination strategy helped the project's popularization among all stakeholders, including a wider audience. Participation in various events, conferences and workshops enhanced the smashHit's presence among the scientific community and helped to find possible future collaborations. Establishing a strong social media presence has been beneficial for raising of awareness about topics such as mobility, semantic technology, data privacy and security, and more. It introduces our innovations to the public and builds a wide network for knowledge exchange and collaboration.

To conclude, the dissemination and communication were on track, and involved all partners' contributions about activities and feedback on their progress. Collaboration, communication and the broader networks between all project partners were essential for the successful dissemination of the smashHit project and has helped build good work ethics, communication skills and recommendation practices for future projects.

6 References

- [1] smashHit consortium, „D8.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan (M3),“ 2020.
- [2] smashHit consortium, „D8.2 Sustainability Plan,“ 2021.
- [3] smashHit consortium, „D8.3 Dissemination and Communication Report (M18),“ 2021.
- [4] smashHit consortium, „D8.5 Sustainability Report (M24),“ 2021.
- [5] smashHit consortium, „D8.6 Sustainability Report (M36),“ 2022.
- [6] A. Remke, „enviroCar: A Citizen Science Platform for Analyzing and Mapping Crowd-Sourced Car Sensor Data“.
- [7] D. Crellin und A. Woolard, E. Kanjo, S. Benford, M. Paxton, A. Chamberlain, D. Fraser, D. Woodgate, MobGeoSen: facilitating personal geosensor data collection and visualization using mobile phones, Springer-Verlag, 2007.
- [8] T. Pellegrini, V. Mireles, S. Steyskal, O. Panasiuk, A. Fensel und S. Kirrane, „Automated Rights Clearance Using Semantic Web Technologies: The DALICC Framework,“ *Semantic Applications* , pp. 203-218, 2018.
- [9] smashHit consortium, „Detailed list of smashHit events and publications, Excel sheet,“ 2022.

smashHit